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Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati

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BIOFIZIKA FANINI O'QITISHDA VIRTUAL LABORATORIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH USTUVORLIGI

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Biofizikaviy tajribalar bo'lajak shifokorlarni laboratoriya sharoitida o'qitish talabalarida diagnoz va davolash jarayonida bemorni anglash va yakka tajribada o'rganishda tabiiy qiziqishni paydo qiladi [1]. Laboratoriya amaliyotini bajarishda mavzuning fizik mohiyatidan tashqari ishning tirik organizm uchun bog'liqligi tushuntiriladi va uni quyidagi bazi bo'limlarda o'z echimini topilishini ko'rish mumkin [2].

Erkin tushish tezlanishni aniqlash orqali jismning erkin tushish paytida va tezlanish bilan yuqoriga ko'tarilishida suyak to'qimalarining mineralsizlanishi va inson organizmining o'ta yuklanishga bardosh bera olishi. Suyuqlik qovushqoqligini aniqlash orqali qon qvushqoqligi tushunchasiga aniqlik kiritish va uni tibbiy diagnostik amaliyotlar uchun foydalanish. O'zgaruvchan zanjirning impedans qarshiligini tirik va o'lik to'qimalarda o'lchash orqali inson mushaklardan tok o'tish jarayonini tushintirish.

Virtual tajribani to'g'ridan - to'g'ri bajarish yoki yangi virtual jarayonni o'zimiz yaratish imkoniga egamiz. Bu ishlarni amalga oshirishda biz dasturlarni ikki xil ko'rinishda foydalanamiz.

1. Virtual simulyatorlar.
2. Modellashtirish dasturlari

Virtual simulyatorlar yordamida biz real voqelikga asoslangan laboratoriya eksperimentlarini amalga oshiramiz. Talim dasturlari va platformalari orqali soddalashtirilgan holda ikki o'lchamli ko'rinishda demonstratsiya qilish va bajarish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lamiz. Virtual simulyator uchun Labster, Phywe, Cobra4 Simulation Software, Praxilabs dasturlarini foydalanish ish unumdorligini oshiradi.

Modellashtirish dasturlari uchun Comsol MultiPhysics, Matlab + Simulink, NEURON yoki GENESIS, PyBioSim dasturlarini bilan haqiqiy manoga yaqin natijalar olinadi.

Virtual laboratoriyalarni rivojlantirish uchun hozirda ko'plab davlatlar yangidan sarmoyalar ajratmoqda va bu 1 - jadvalda ko'rsatilgan.

Virtual laboratoriyalarni rivojlantirish uchun ajratilgan mablag'lar

1 - jadval

Platforma	Ajratilgan mablag'	Davlat	Yillar
Labster	50 million \$	Daniya	2021 - yil
Phet Interactive Simulations	20 million \$	AQSh	2010 - 2020 - yil
Virtual Labs	12 million \$	Hindston	2012 - yil
Simbio	5 - 7 million \$	AQSh	2010 - yil

Chemcollective	3 – 5 million \$	AQSh	2003 – 2011 – yillar
LabXchange	7 million \$	AQSh	2018 – 2022 – yillar
OpenLab	2 – 4 million \$	AQSh	2015 – yil

Virtual laboratoriyalar orasida foydalanish darajasi bo'yicha etakchilik qilayotgan platformalarning umumiy reytingini 2 – jadval orqali tanishib chiqishimiz mumkin.

Virtual laboratoriyalardan umumiy foydalanish reytingi va qo'llanilish sohalari
2 – jadval

Platforma	Baholash/Protsentlarda(%)	Sohalar
Labster	30 – 35 %	Yuqori sifatli simulyatsiyalar bilan akademik sohada etakchi.
Phet Interactive Simulations	25 – 30 %	Bepul va foydalanish mumkin bo'lgan simulyatsiyalar, keng ko'lamli fanlar.
Virtual Labs	15 – 20 %	Rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda mashhur, ko'plab fanlarni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi.
Simbio	10 – 15 %	Biologiya, interaktiv laboratoriyalar bo'yicha mutaxassislik.
Chemcollective	10 – 12 %	Kimyo bo'yicha mutaxassislik, o'rta maktab va universitet talabalari uchun.
Bioman Biology	5 – 10 %	Maktab o'quvchilari uchun o'yin yondashuvi, kontentning mavjudligi.
LabXchange	5 – 8 %	Bepul kirish, Garvard universiteti tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanadi.

Zamonaviy tibbiy ta'limda biofizika fanini o'qitishda virtual laboratoriyalarni qo'llash talabalarning ilmiy tafakkurini shakllantirishda, kasbiy qiziqishini oshirishda va nazariy bilimlarni amaliyot bilan mustahkamlashda muhim vositaga aylangan [3]. Virtual simulyatorlar va modellashtirish dasturlari orqali talabalarda eksperimentlarni real va yaqin sharoitda bajarish, hamda murakkab biofizik jarayonlarni chuqur anglash imkoniyati yaratilmoqda.

Jahon tajribasida ham ushbu yo'nalishga katta e'tibor qaratilayotgani, davlatlar tomonidan millionlab mablag'larning ajratilishi bilan tasdiqlanadi. Labster, Phet Interactive Simulations, Virtual Labs kabi platformalarning faoliyati bu borada yetakchi o'rinda turadi. Ular orqali tibbiyot yo'nalishidagi talabalar nafaqat nazariy bilimlarga ega bo'ladilar, balki ularni mustaqil ravishda amaliy mashg'ulotlarda sinab ko'rish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lmoqdalar.

Virtual laboratoriyalar yordamida amalga oshirilayotgan bu yondashuv kelajakda tibbiyot sohasida yanada malakali va tajribali mutaxassislarni tayyorlashda muhim omil bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Shu bois, biofizika fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy texnologiyalarni keng joriy etish va ularni yanada takomillashtirish dolzarb masala bo'lib qolmoqda.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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A SYSTEMATIC APPROACH TO THE TEACHING OF NUCLEAR ENERGY IN A MODULAR WAY IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Modular teaching of nuclear power plant engineering in higher education involves the selection of a combination of methods, approaches and cognitive approaches that enable students to become experts in their profession, a systems approach that allows them to view and understand each object as a system.

Systems analysis is a research method based on a comprehensive view of the relationships between the elements of a nuclear power plant as a whole, i.e. a sequential view of the elements of a nuclear power plant [1].

The requirement for system adaptation is not only the development of individual components, but also the development of the entire system as a whole. The focus is therefore on the standardisation of all internal and external parameters of the object under consideration, the coordination of their various properties and the management processes [2].

The basis of the system communication is the close integration of the activities of teachers and students in the educational process at universities, which ultimately leads to high efficiency in the deep mastering of the subject by students and is an effective result of the use of traditional and modern interactive methods.

Modular education of students at universities should be based on system adaptation and take into account the following factors (Table 1).

1-Table

Optimization of the educational process. Methodological principles.		
Without the coherence of the content, that is, the	The alternation of the cognitive (information block) and educational-professional	Develops the skills of systematization of undergraduate and graduate